

Science Communication took the stage during the 15th International Society for Biosafety Research (ISBR) Symposium

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Held in Tarragona, Spain, between 01-04 April 2019, the 15th ISBR Symposium gathered together nearly 300 attendees comprising biotechnology researchers, regulators, NGOs, farmers and science communicators from around the world. It was a unique scientific conference where science communication took to the main stage and opened the event. In this short note, I review the plenary session, keynote lectures and a workshop dedicated to public communication of modern biotechnology.

Keywords: Public engagement with science and technology, Public understanding of science and technology, Risk communication.

The **International Society for Biosafety Research** (ISBR) promotes scientifically sound research that supports biosafety assessment. This international society fosters communication among scientists who study plants, animals, and microbes with new characteristics due to altered DNA and produced using modern biotechnology. At the same time, the ISBR advocates for constructive dialogue on important science-based biosafety issues associated with genetically modified organisms (GMOs).

In agriculture, GMOs have enabled increased yields and reduced pesticide usage [Klümper and Qaim, 2014]. For these reasons, GMOs are among the innovations with higher adoption worldwide [Huesing et al. 2015]. Despite increasing scientific evidence that they are safe to eat and not harmful to the environment, public opposition to GMOs does not seem to be diminishing [Soninno and Sharry, 2017] and they continue to be the subject of controversy. Given the increasingly important role of agricultural biotechnology to achieve sustainable farming, it has become more necessary than ever to contribute to an informed public understanding of agricultural sciences [Blancke et al. 2017].

Science communication is one technique being used in the effort for the public to support agricultural biotechnologists and their work. However, science communication has been predicated on the assumption that ignorance is the bases of a lack of societal support for various issues in science and technology [Simis et al., 2016]. Certainly, this knowledge deficit model in agricultural biotechnology communication should be move toward more effective science communication efforts.

In response, the first plenary session of the 15th ISBR Symposium was dedicated to science communication and engagement with policy and public audiences. The session was organised by Hennie Groenewald (Biosafety South Africa) and Jennifer Anderson (Corteva Agriscience, USA), and included four keynote lectures.

The opening was given by **Jack Bobo** (Futurity, Maryland, USA). In 2015, Jack was named by Scientific American as one of the 100 most influential people in biotechnology, and had previously served as a senior advisor at the USA's Department of State. Bobo provoked reflections from the very beginning of his talk "*Can agriculture save the planet before it destroys it?*" by stating that agriculture is the biggest human activity on earth and the one with the most negative impact. At the same time, he noted that there's nothing more critical for our daily survival. Bobo argued that innovation and new technologies in agriculture can save the planet. However, the changes that are inherent to these innovations appear to scare the public, especially how our food is improved. He considered that consumers have never cared more, nor known less, about the food they eat. And because people love innovation as much as they despise change, conversations should be based on former rather than the latter. But how can this conversation be shifted? Rather than beating people with science, Bobo proposed that scientists and communicators must lead them to knowledge. The rationale of this, Bobo stated, is that we all love to learn things, but we don't like to be told things. For instance, it is better to show that all food contains chemicals instead of beating people over their heads with facts and data. "How we frame that conversation now will shape the future of food", Bobo categorically said. He added that it is much better to frame the conversation around shared values rather than focusing on modern genetic engineering techniques. He concluded that the next 30 years will be the most important for agriculture and if we get involved, agriculture can save the world.

Following the session theme, **John Besley** (Michigan State University, East Lansing, USA), who helps science communicators to be more strategic, offered guidance aimed at improving the perceptions of plant scientists and the agronomic sciences. During his talk "*How do you want agricultural biotechnology science and scientists to be perceived?*" Besley provided evidence-based information from the perspective of strategic science communication research on how to better communicate facts. He compared engagement tactics versus cognitive engagement, and explained the effect of aggressive risk communication in the context of science blogs. "Should scientists talk about GMOs nicely?" was one of the driven question. He provided data supporting the fact that being aggressive does not accomplish science communication goals [Yuan *et al.* 2016]. He strongly recommended setting up behavioural goals before expending any effort in communicating GMO-related data.

Are GMOs guilty until proven innocent? Will scientists get a fair chance to demonstrate the opposite? These questions were asked by **Mahaletchumy Arujanan** (Malaysian Biotechnology Information Centre) during her engaging lecture. Also named by Scientific American as one of the 100 most influential people in biotechnology in 2015, Arujanan emphasised that a biotech

communicator must first establish a relationship with its audience before sharing information. She argued that this should be done in sequential steps: communicators must show empathy, build trust, share values and interests, and finally provide knowledge or data – in that specific order. Only in this way can cultural cognition and people’s cognitive dissonance be challenged. This is because, when information is complex, people tend to make decisions based on values and reject things that don’t agree with prior beliefs. In this sense, Arujanan added that Aristotle's theory of persuasions is still valid for successful science communication: 10 % ethos (credibility), 25% logos (logic) and 65% pathos (emotion).

Another perspective on communication and engagement, from the point of view of a regulatory agency, was provided by **Ben Durham** (Department of Science and Technology, South Africa). During the fourth and last keynote lecture, Durham addressed the critical role of communication and engagement from a biotechnology policy perspective in the developing world. “The truth is not actually very important. Society has a much different perspective on truth than science,” he underlined. Leadership, communication and engagement remain critical as building blocks, he summarized, but this combination need to be culturally adapted to the local setting.

Additional to the keynote lectures, the **Alliance for Science** (Cornell University, USA) complemented the Science Communication plenary with a workshop entitled “*Real-world Biosafety Communication and Engagement*”. It brought together farmers from Bangladesh, Ghana, India, Nigeria, and South Africa to highlight the deep divisions between farmers who have and those who do not have modern agricultural tools. The workshop described experiences within a variety of contexts associated with biotechnology innovation: research and development projects; policy-making and regulations; business development, trade and marketing, and grassroots advocacy campaigns. It provided academic reflections from science communication on these practical experiences.

In summary, all the speakers agreed that no silver bullet exists to effectively communicate agricultural biotechnology. People believe in scientific ideas because they feel an affinity for the scientific community, not because they have truly and thoroughly evaluated all of the evidence. In consequence, the speakers suggested that as part of their professional responsibilities, scientists should engage in science communication, particularly through methods grounded in social science research such as value-sharing and storytelling. What was apparent to me was that the emerging broad landscape of agricultural innovation needs a grassroots community for science communication past the deficit model approach.

It was great to see that science communication took the stage and opened this prestigious symposium, as a recognition of its vital importance for the success of modern biotechnology.

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